

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF THE FUTURE TEACHER OF ARTS

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Abstract. *This article was put forward to answer the question of what should be the result of methodological training of teachers. Methodical training teaches how to get out of the problem situation caused by the conflict between ensuring the quality of education and not solving it by means of traditional methods, that is, by increasing the amount of information to be learned. In addition, the role of language education in the development of professional competences and the ability to solve communication issues relevant in everyday, educational, industrial and cultural life with the help of a foreign language, and to achieve communication goals with the help of language and speech tools were considered.*

Keywords: *future teacher, methodology, educational work, knowledge, information, skill, light shade, color perspective, composition.*

They form their knowledge and skills through the practical processes of preparing the future art teacher for professional management. At the same time, it is important to be able to apply the theoretical and scientific knowledge gained in practical training.

A clear example of this is, "further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" defined in the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

In our republic, art is given so much attention, so the art teacher should be as well. Therefore, the role of professors and teachers in strengthening the knowledge of students in higher educational institutions during the professional training of the future art teacher is incomparable. It is an important process that the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by the students help in the correct orientation. Therefore, the knowledge gained from professional skills will help future specialists to achieve the highest results. It is important that the future teacher of arts can skillfully apply the knowledge acquired during his studies in his professional activities, and at the same time, he loves his profession. At the same time, intelligently drawing conclusions from the mistakes made will pave the way for a better result in the future.

Pedagogical preparation of future visual arts teacher in professional management training changes over time. During their activities, they should have modern technological and pedagogical support in line with the times. In practical training, it is important for future specialists to know the following in order to strengthen their professional knowledge; understanding the laws of art, analyzing fine art works, promoting modern ideas in fine art, effective use of new methods and tools, being able to use innovative educational technologies, and developing professional practical skills.

Theoretical knowledge is closely related to the practical processes of training a future art teacher for professional management. Searching for new approaches to the problems encountered in practical training, creative self-development and improvement of the individual is the main priority.

K.M. Duray-Novakova analyzed the issue of formation of teacher's professional training and broadly explained the legal result of the concepts of professional training, development of professional orientation, familiarization with professions, professional education, education and upbringing, professional identity. According to him, preparation for pedagogical activity is a complex educational system, the basis of which is a positive attitude of students to the future teaching profession, the goal of sufficiently stable activity, professional pedagogical knowledge, skills, abilities, and their practical application [2;78-b].

Another aspect of the preparation of a future art teacher for professional management is that the pedagogue intelligently manages the process of independent performance of the task by the students, carefully observes it, and if necessary invites to live communication. During the logical thinking of the students, their live observation, the frame of mind is consistently taken into account by the pedagogue, and at the end of the study, the scores or grades given to the active students are announced [3;19-b;].

In the educational processes of fine arts, the future fine arts teacher will achieve the intended result if he effectively uses modern interactive teaching methods and modern educational technologies to improve the quality and efficiency of the lesson.

Aspects that are important for the future arts teacher to know during the practical training of composition in higher educational institutions in improving the practical processes of preparation for professional management are the legal rules of composition, the formation of educational technologies and its modern structure; characteristics of traditional and non-traditional educational technologies; science- and person-oriented technologies of education; didactic game technologies; educational technologies that develop and shape critical thinking; modular teaching technology; distance learning technology; international integration of educational process organization technologies; technologicalization of the educational process; communication culture and pedagogical technique of the teacher; is to teach theoretical and practical knowledge about the problems of the modern education system and technologies in a coherent and continuous manner [116; 19-b].

One of the good aspects of the profession of art teacher is that the free engagement in creative activities brings satisfaction and happiness to a person. This process gives him a calm feeling of respect and satisfaction for his profession. When the future visual arts teacher sees the results of the students' creative work during their professional career, their self-confidence increases even more when they acquire science and high positions.

When it comes to the methodical stages of preparation for professional management of the future art teacher in the higher education system, they can be conditionally divided into two parts.

1. Among the main tasks of practical training of visual arts for students: to feel the attractiveness of nature and preserve it, to develop aesthetic and artistic taste; development of artistic thought, creative ability and imagination, introduction to the theoretical foundations of art (light and shadow, color theory, perspective, composition); skill building; development of observation, visual memory, ability to guess, spatial and pictorial imagination, abstract and logical thinking; to teach to read visual and practical architectural works of art; arousing interest in art, teaching to appreciate and love it.

2. One of the additional tasks of visual art classes is to help to know existence; implementation of the ideology of national pride and national independence; moral and ethical behavior of students;

implementation of work, physical education; is to strengthen the role of the future art teacher in guiding children to various professions and trades.

The future teacher of visual arts first of all performs the task of teaching and educating students in his subject as a subject of general education. Also, the school's visual arts teacher teaches students to look at things carefully, to analyze the shape, color and essence of objects based on the teaching of this subject. A visual arts teacher teaches students to observe, perceive, and pay close attention to things and events.

A future art teacher organizes art classes and workshops. It is necessary to prepare visual aids in different content. Because it is necessary to draw a picture of what the student perceives and sees according to the content of visual arts [4; 35-b]. I should also say that the school visual arts lesson is organized in 5 types, 5 types, 5 characters. Organizing and conducting such diverse classes creates many difficulties. Therefore, the complexity of the lesson materials requires the teacher to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. An experienced teacher finds time for everything. The future teacher is actively involved in organizing the lesson until the end. The teacher, starting from the preparation for the lesson, tries to convey it to the students in an easy, short, reasonable way. The future teacher should work with each student individually during the lesson.

A teacher should demonstrate good drawing by expressing it on the classroom board or in step-by-step drawings prepared at home. The future teacher should pay attention to everything in the organization of the lesson and correct all the shortcomings before the lesson begins. It is necessary to follow each step correctly in conducting the lesson. Every minute should be used effectively. It is necessary to carry out all the educational activities from checking the students' knowledge to giving homework.

The main task of the future visual arts teacher is to develop children's developing visual skills, and he is the first person who teaches them how to hold a pencil, put a drawing notebook on the desk, observe the object and event to be drawn, and write the impressions on paper [5; 118-b].

He is also a pedagogue who introduces the student to independent work in drawing, initiative and creativity. Along with teaching drawing, the teacher gives students beauty and aesthetic education. Teaches to be in love with work, creativity, one's country, country, and people. The fine arts teacher instills in children the feelings of being honest, pure, faithful, truthful, and starts them towards Great spirituality. In carrying out and implementing these, the teacher works on his own initiative.

A future teacher of visual arts should be able to listen well, be able to reason, and also be able to read, write, speak and draw at a high level. In general, a school art teacher differs from science teachers in his creativity, initiative and fairness. Because he should always be busy with drawing, creating a work of art himself. He hesitates to create something new every day. Also, on his own initiative, he creates a cabinet of visual arts. He makes something (didactic material, demonstration tool) every day. He is engaged in increasing the fund of Natura. He also works on improving his pedagogical skills.

A skilled art teacher of the school adjusts his lessons to work on the basis of modern pedagogical technology.

In conclusion, analysis, observation and research today show that the basics of mastering the secrets of improving the methodical training of a teacher in visual arts have a positive effect in the process of studying in higher and secondary special educational institutions, the existence of opportunities in it, theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and mastery of skills proves to be highly

effective. Therefore, improving the methodical training of the future fine art teacher places a high responsibility on higher and secondary special educational institutions that train such specialists.

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